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DEVELOPMENT OF CULTURAL COMPETENCES OF HIGHER EDUCATION STUDENTS USING INTERACTIVE METHODS

Abstract. Today, the curriculum regulates the number of hours allocated to lessons using interactive teaching methods. Educational-methodological complex/complexes of sciences reflect the whole spectrum of interactive forms of teaching. However, the problem of increasing the efficiency of their use in the educational process is still relevant.

Keywords: Educational-methodological complex, imitation, problem speech.

We consider interactive educational technologies as ways of acquiring knowledge, developing skills and abilities in the process of interaction and interaction between the pedagogue and the student as subjects of educational activity. Their essence is that they rely not only on the processes of perception, memory and attention, but also, above all, on creative and productive thinking, behavior and communication. In this, the educational process in the innovative educational environment is organized in such a way that students learn to communicate, learn to interact with each other and other people, learn critical thinking, solve complex problems based on the analysis of pedagogical situations, situational professional tasks and relevant information.. In interactive educational technologies, the role of the teacher and learners (the subject of mutual activity instead of the object of influence), as well as the role of information (information is not a goal, but a means of mastering actions and operations) changes significantly. All interactive educational technologies are divided into non-simulated and simulated types. Classification is based on the sign of restoration (imitation) of the context of professional pedagogical activity, its presentation/expression as a model in education. Non-imitation technologies do not involve building models of the studied phenomenon or activity. The basis of imitation (imitation) technologies is imitation or imitation-game modeling, that is, re-development/repetition of processes occurring in the real system with one or another degree of relevance/compatibility/adequacy in educational conditions.

The effectiveness of using interactive forms of education in the innovative educational environment is ensured by the implementation of the following pedagogical conditions: creating a dialogic space in the organization of the educational process; use of socio-psychological principles of transition in

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educational and extracurricular activities; control of personal characteristics and professional orientation of students; development of teachers' psychological readiness to use interactive forms aimed at developing students' internal activity of teaching.

"Problem speech" implies setting a problem, a problematic situation and solving them later. In the problem lecture, the conflicts of real life are modeled by expressing them in theoretical concepts. The main purpose of such a lecture is to gain knowledge with direct and positive result/effective participation of students. Modeled problems may include scientific, social, and professional problems related to the specific content of the educational material. Setting (giving) a problem encourages students to think actively, to try to answer the question independently, arouses interest in the presented material and activates students' attention.

"Debate-seminar" implies a collective discussion of a problem in order to determine reliable ways to solve it. The debate-seminar is held in the form of a dialog between its participants. It requires high mental activity, inculcates/trains the skills of holding a debate, discussing a problem, defending your views and beliefs, expressing your thoughts concisely and clearly. The roles of practitioners in the debate-seminar may be different.

"Learning discussion" is one of the methods of problem-based education. It is used in the analysis of problematic situations when it is necessary to give a simple and unambiguous answer to the question, and it is assumed that there are alternative answers. It is advisable to use the method of cooperative teaching (educational cooperation) in order to involve all those who participated in the discussion. This methodology is based on interactive teaching/learning with students working together in small groups. The basic idea of educational cooperation is very simple: students combine their intellectual efforts to perform a common task or achieve a common goal (for example, to find a solution to a problem). The working technology of the study group in educational/educational cooperation can be as follows:

- pose a problem.
- development of small groups (microgroups of 5-7 people), distribution of roles in them, explanations of the teacher's expected participation in the discussion;
- discuss the problem in microgroups;
- giving/presenting the results of the discussion to the whole study group;
- continue the discussion and summarize/conclude the results.

"Brainstorming" aims to collect as many ideas as possible, to free students from thinking inertia, to activate creative thinking, to overcome the usual flow of thoughts when solving a problem. "Brainstorming" makes it possible to significantly increase the efficiency of creating new ideas in the study group. The main principles and rules of this method are the absolute prohibition of criticism

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of the ideas proposed by the participants, as well as the encouragement of various comments and even jokes.

"Didactic game" serves as an important pedagogical tool for activating the teaching process in the educational environment of HEIs. In the course of the didactic game, the student should perform work/actions/movements similar to the work/actions/movements that may occur in his professional activity. As a result, accumulation of knowledge, updating and turning them into skills, accumulation of personal experience and its development takes place. Didactic game technology consists of three stages. Involvement in a didactic game, playful development of professional activity according to its model helps the systematic and holistic development of the profession. Internship with the performance of a position/official role is an active teaching method of teaching, in which the field of professional activity, reality itself as a "model", and imitation mainly implies the performance of a role (position). The main condition of the internship is to perform certain actions/work/activities under the supervision of a teacher in real production conditions.

"Imitation training" refers to training and polishing certain professional skills and competencies for working with various technical tools and devices. The situation/situation and environment of the professional activity is simulated and the technical means (trainers, measuring equipment, etc.) itself serves as a "model".

"Game-based design" is a practical activity during which engineering, construction, technological, social and other types of projects are developed in a game environment that reproduces the reality/real situation as much as possible. This method is characterized by a high degree of convergence/combination of individual and joint work of students. Creating a joint/common project for a group requires, on the one hand, knowledge of the technology of the design process, and on the other hand, the ability to communicate and maintain/maintain interpersonal relationships for professional problem-solving.

"Computer technologies of education" are the processes of collecting, processing, storing and transmitting information to the student through a computer. Today, such technological trends are developing. In it, the computer performs the following tasks:

- means of providing educational material to students for the purpose of knowledge transfer;
- a means of providing information to educational processes as an additional source of information/information;
- a means of determining the level of knowledge and controlling the assimilation of educational material;
- a universal simulator for developing the skills of practical application of knowledge;
- means of conducting educational experiments and business games on the subject of study;

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- one of the most important elements in the future professional activity of the student.

Interactive forms of education play a special role in the teaching of humanities, which in turn has a system-forming effect on the development of cultural competences of future pedagogues. The role of humanities block sciences in the development is determined by their contribution/help to:

- development of students' creative activity;
- development of personal readiness to apply knowledge and skills;
- development of communicative and organizational skills;
- development of universal (humanistic) values;
- expansion of environmental awareness;
- mastering knowledge of psychology, pedagogical psychology;
- the ability to receive continuous education throughout life and re-learn when necessary, etc.

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